

First steps with VinciBot

Pablo Duo | 19/12/2023

The students' first contact with a robot should be to get to know what sensors and actuators are, as well as to introduce the Matatalab platform and its basic programming blocks.

In a staggered way and during 7 activities with different challenges, students will link mathematical concepts such as turns, degrees, geometric figures, divisions, repetitions... with programming blocks such as loops, patterns and colour sensors, distances... to end up carrying out 2 STEAM projects with the VinciBot robot and LEGO pieces that they will end up presenting to their classmates.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

To know the basic concepts of programming and robotics.

Simplify repetitive steps such as loops.

Incorporating mathematical skills and abilities into programming.

Collaboratively produce an innovative and creative product using computational thinking.

Developing creative thinking.

Presenting a design.

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

COMMUNICATION

CRITICAL THINKING

CREATIVITY

AGE GROUP

From 10 to 12

SCENARIO LANGUAGE

English

TOTAL DURATION

15 hours

SUBJECTS

ART

DESIGN - TECHNOLOGY

MATHEMATICS

VINCIBOT - MATATALAB PROJECT (PRIMARY EDUCATION 5TH AND 6TH GRADES)

Activity 1. My first steps with a robot

INTERACT & INSTRUCT

C'S OF EDUCATION

COMMUNICATION

CRITICAL THINKING

TOOLS

Interactive whiteboard.

VinciBot robot.

Matatalab platform for programming.

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher-led

DESCRIPTION

On the interactive whiteboard, the teacher interacts with the sensors and actuators of a robot, simulating the sensory organs and the human locomotor system.

Subsequently, the VinciBot Robot and the Matatalab programming platform are presented.

Images in the following link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1airKu2z38KNXi98IMiir0QKwiUX9T8Bo?usp=sharing>

Activity 2. My first programmes with VinciBot

INTERACT & INSTRUCT

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

CRITICAL THINKING

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer

Traditional whiteboard

5 sets of VinciBot

Grid panel

Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Private, limited distraction

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher at the side

DESCRIPTION

The first steps in programming are oriented towards using forward, backward and turning movements. Using the grid panel provided with VinciBot, the students will program the following instructions.

- Go from point A to point B without turning.

- To go from point A to point B with turns.

- Go from point A to point B with turns and returns.

In this session, we coordinate with the maths teacher to explain the combined operations with brackets, for example, going from point A to point B with 20 cm distance and return is equal to $(20+20)$ or 2×20 .

Images of activity 2 and 3 in the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1kb0nK042QSSV823Rw0wzpj_e_CeHx8yIT?usp=sharing

Activity 3. My first project

PRESENT & SHARE

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

COMMUNICATION

CREATIVITY

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer

Traditional whiteboard

5 sets of VinciBot

Grid panel

Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher at the side

DESCRIPTION

In this session, before launching the challenge, the sound programming blocks are shown how they work.

The teacher launches a challenge on the grid panel.

The VinciBot is an ambulance that is in the "purple" grid but receives a call from an emergency from a house in the "blue grid" where the VinciBot must stop and sound the siren to pick up the patient and then go to the hospital, which is in the "green" grid.

The students in groups of 3-4 start programming and then present it to their classmates. If a group finishes first, they are extended by asking the robot to return to the initial position.

Images of activity 2 and 3 can be found in the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1kb0nK042QSSV823Rw0wzpj_e_CeHx8yIT?usp=sharing

Activity 4. Mandalas

INTERACT & INSTRUCT

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

CRITICAL THINKING

CREATIVITY

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer

Traditional whiteboard

5 sets of VinciBot

A3 sheets of paper

Marker pen

Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher at the side

DESCRIPTION

In the first part (1 hour) we explain to the students how to program and draw geometric figures with the Vincibot, the total path corresponds to the perimeter.

Subsequently, we explain to them how to save programming blocks to make a square, triangle, pentagon... With repeating loops and rotating the corresponding degrees to add up to 360 degrees. For example a square with 4 sides is to repeat 4 times (move X steps and rotate 90°).

In this session, we draw on A3 size paper the figures.

Finally, a challenge is given to the groups: How do you make a circle?

In the second part (1 hour), we remember the previous steps but this time we make loops of geometric figures (see video) to make mandalas that are presented to other groups.

Images of activity 4 in the following link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1REt8Hhau-4zUt08UHQLA5-aaJ2oVLzWu?usp=sharing>

Activity 5- Sumo Fighting

CREATE

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

COMMUNICATION

CRITICAL THINKING

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer
 Traditional whiteboard
 5 sets of VinciBot
 Black adhesive tape
 Colour board
 Plastic cups
 Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher-led

DESCRIPTION

This activity is divided into 3 parts:

A) 1 hour- First, students are shown the colour sensor and test with their hands how the Matatalab detector shows the distance between the robot and the hand and how it varies. In addition, they are challenged to make the lights of the VinciBot change according to the colour panel on the robot.

They are given the challenge that depending on the colour detected, the name of the colour will appear on the main screen.

B) 1 hour- In this session, students learn how to make a robot turn 180°, i.e. turn around when it detects black on the floor, making back and forth movements. Subsequently, they perform the same task but on a closed circle, but this time the robot will rotate randomly between 135° and 270°, so it will not make back-and-forth movements.

C) 1 hour- With the previous knowledge, students must program a robot without leaving the circle to eject plastic cups from the circle itself (See video). How?

- By always turning on its axis.
- If it detects an obstacle (cup) within 30 cm, it will move forward until it detects a black line on the ground.
- It will go backwards, 10 cm and turn again until it detects a new obstacle.

Images of activity 5 in the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/12G_rllc7wKm8zc7HS3Fjo2M1Y7SgfEbE?usp=sharing

3
HOURS
0
MINUTES

Activity 6- STEAM Tango Dance

CREATE

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

COMMUNICATION

CREATIVITY

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer
 Traditional whiteboard
 5 sets of VinciBot
 Lego pieces kit
 Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher at the side

DESCRIPTION

This 3-hour task consists of 4 parts:

A) Explanation and demonstration of the Lego Kit.

B) Selection by vote of the robot that the students wish to assemble. In this case they choose the dancer.

During this session the teacher will be the guide because the students ask about the pieces and their sizes, although they have the Matatalab guide to go step by step.

C) Program the programming blocks with Matatalab.

D) Show their classmates the result of how the robot works.

Images of activity 6 in the following link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1avxF-ogh7WV9nLjyvASKZNdVuUdcEWR?usp=sharing>

Activity 7 - basketball shooter

CREATE

C'S OF EDUCATION

COLLABORATION

COMMUNICATION

CRITICAL THINKING

CREATIVITY

TOOLS

Interactive digital display and computer

Traditional whiteboard

5 sets of VinciBot

Lego parts kit

Plastic cups

Ping-pong ball

Matatalab website

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Small groups

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher at the side

DESCRIPTION

This 3-hour task consists of 4 parts:

A) Explanation of the challenge of making a basket launcher with VinciBot. Allow time for the groups to think about the parts and the prototype they are going to use.

B) Free time for groups to create and assemble the VinciBot parts.

C) Programming the programming blocks with Matatalab and testing phase by groups.

D) Present the results of how the robot works to their classmates.

Images of activity 7 in the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1EJLw1Yp0kCl_uG9nvOONyK_0oB7Ocxv1?usp=sharing

Final evaluation test

ASSESSMENT & FEEDBACK

C'S OF EDUCATION

COMMUNICATION

TOOLS

Tablets

Form provided by European Schoolnet

SPACE FORMAT

Public

POSITION OF LEARNERS

Alone

ROLE OF TEACHER

Teacher-led

DESCRIPTION

Students, under the supervision and support of the teacher, access and complete the final form offered by European Schoolnet.

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